

Appendix 3: Guidance on data reporting

A3.1 Data reporting guidance document

Guidance – what and how to report

Two files have been developed for the test reporting of AMR data.

"**WISE_AMR_template.xlsx**" where you will report all the measured values and related and information.

- Sampling site information is reported in the sheet "Site_AMR".
- Sample and analysis data are reported in the sheet "DisaggregatedData_AMR".

"**WISE_AMR_guidance.pdf**" (**this file**) where the guidance with instructions and where applicable, the vocabulary/ code list. This file is a guide to how and what to report.

General information:

- Please use the guidance and instructions to ensure correct and reporting and efficient data processing.
- Copy-paste from the vocabulary to the template is *recommended* to avoid spelling mistakes.
- Information that does not fit in any of the elements in the template, can be entered into the field "Remarks".
- The guidance is provided with both a pdf-file and an excel-file, and the content is identical.

How to read the guidance file:

The guidance file contains **two** main tables:

1. "Table Site_AMR": Contains a description of the information to be entered in the first template sheet, named "Site_AMR".
2. "Table DisaggregatedData_AMR": Contains a description of the information to be entered in the second template sheet, named "DisaggregatedData_AMR".

The table descriptions contain, for each field...

- Short name: a short, but user-friendly name of the element (with spaces).
- Identifier: a short and machine-friendly name of the element (without spaces).
- Mandatory: 'Mandatory' = a number or text must be entered; 'Optional' = can be left empty.
- Unique record [Primary key]: The combination of elements that identify a unique record. To avoid duplicates, all records (rows) must have different combinations of the elements with Unique record [Primary key] = "yes".
- Vocabulary: indicates a vocabulary (code list) exists for the given element. If "yes", the vocabulary for that element is given in a separate table in the guidance.
- Data type: number or text.
- Definition: a short description of the element.
- Methodology: a longer description of how to obtain and specify the information to be entered.
- URL: If applicable, a link to relevant information in existing EEA data dictionaries.

How to report data in the template:

1. Open the template "**WISE_AMR_template.xlt**", and save a copy locally as " WISE_AMR_<country code>_<YYYY-MM-DD>.xlsx ". (Example: WISE_AMR_NO_2024-03-01.xlsx)
2. The first **template sheet "Site_AMR"** is for reporting spatial information etc. for sampling sites.
 - a. Each record (row) in the template sheet "Site_AMR" should represents one sampling site. This means that each record here can be linked to one or more records in the second sheet (measured values).
 - b. Each field (column) in the template sheet "Site_AMR" is described in the guidance table "Table Site_AMR" (as a transposed version of the reporting table).

- c. For fields with "Vocabulary" = "yes", a code list can be found in the guidance. Copy-paste from the code list is recommended to avoid spelling mistakes.
 - d. The field "Site ID" must be identical in both template sheets, "Site_AMR" and "DisaggregatedData_AMR".
 - e. For fields with Vocabulary = "(WFD)": If the site is already reported under WFD, then this information can be obtained from the WFD reporting (by reporters or by EEA).
 - f. An example has been filled in as additional guidance. Please delete the example record(s).
3. The second **template sheet "DisaggregatedData_AMR"** is for reporting of measured values and associated information on sampling and analysis.
- a. Every record (row) in the template sheet "DisaggregatedData_AMR" should represent one measured value.
 - b. Repliate samples (from the same site and date) can be distinguished by different values in the field "Sample identifier".
 - c. (See points 2c-f above)
- Please upload the correctly filled-in and renamed template to the assigned folder in "Reporting" > the folder for your landcode in the Eionet Teams channel "WG Antimicrobial Resistance"
(<https://eea1.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/-EXT-Eionet/Shared%20Documents/WG%20Antimicrobial%20Resistance/Other%20activities/AMR%20data%20reporting/Reporting?csf=1&web=1&e=qpLWqe>).

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Short name	Identifier (element)	Mandatory	Unique record [Primary key]	Vocabulary	Data type	Definition	Methodology	URL
2	Country code	CountryCode	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Text	Country code for the country of the sampling site.	See URL for vocabulary.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/datasets/latest/WISE-SoE_Biology/tables/BiologyEQRClassificationProcedure/elements/countryCode
3	Site ID	NationalSiteID	Mandatory	Yes	No	Text	Code for the sampling site. Use different site IDs for different records.	The NationalSiteID can be made by data providers. The ID can contain letters, numbers and/or underscore (no spaces or special characters). NationalSiteID must be entered in both sheets in the reporting template: Site_AMR (one record for each NationalSiteID) and DisaggregatedData_AMR (NationalSiteID repeated for each sample).	NA
4	WWTP ID	WasteWaterTreatmentPlantID	Optional	No	No	Text	If sampling in regards to a WWTP, name the WWTP. This will be if sampling from a water source affected of a WWTP, or water or waste water from WWTP.	If not relevant to report WWTP, enter default value 1. If relevant to report WWTP, please check this website (https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/maps-and-charts/urban-waste-water-treatment-maps-3), search the state and find the treatment plant in the list provided in the search field. Enter the WWTP ID in the following format : <ID>. Example: D0055	NA

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
5	Longitude	Longitude	Mandatory	No	No	Number	The coordinate of the sampling site (East).	Use the common geodetic datum ETRS89. WGS84 should be used for overseas areas and can be used for TCM data as well. Use negative values for coordinates west of the Greenwich Meridian (0°). Please round the coordinates to 4 - 5 decimal places, depending on your input data precision (0.0001° = about 10 m). Utilize GPS (do not recommend google maps) to find coordinates. ETC can calculate between the two geodetic datum if necessary.	NA
6	Latitude	Latitude	Mandatory	No	No	Number	The coordinate of the sampling site (North).	See Methodology for "Longitude"	NA
7	Water body category code	parameterWaterBodyCategory	Mandatory	No	Yes	Text	Water body category code, as defined in the codelist.	See table "Water body category"	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/parameterWaterBodyCategory
8	WWTP name	WasteWaterTreatmentPlantName	Mandatory	No	No			If not relevant to report WWTP, enter default value 1. If relevant, enter the WWTP name in the following format: <UWWTP name>. Example: "Westport Waste Water Treatment Plant". For further instructions, see element "WasteWaterTreatmentPlantID".	NA
9	National site name	NationalSiteName	Optional	No	No	Text	Name of sampling site.	In difference from NationalSiteID, you can use spaces in this element.	
10	Distance from sampling site to AMR source	LengthFromSource	Optional	No	No	Number	Distance of the sampling site from the AMR source (if applicable)	Distance in m	NA

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
11	Location of sampling site	SiteLocation				Text	Location of sampling site in relation to the AMR source (if applicable)	Example: upstream, downstream in the river from the AMR source, such as a WWTP.	NA
			Optional	No	No				
12	WFD station name	WFDstation				Text		Countries that have reported in WFD database before can extract the WFD data from WFD database if you want to, but for those of you who have not used it before can consider this as free text and /or leave elements empty. This applies for all field marked "(WFD database)".	NA
			Optional	No	(WFD database)				
13	WFD station name	WFD_EU_CD				Text			NA
			Optional	No	(WFD database)				
14	River name	RiverName				Text	National name of river.	For stations belonging to water bodies on a WISE main river, pls. include the river name or ID being unique and consistent from source to mouth of this river.	NA
			Optional	No	(WFD database)				
15	Water Body ID	WaterBodyID				Text	Water Body ID	National identification code of water body (if available) in which station is located.	NA
			Optional	No	(WFD database)				
16	Water Body Name	WaterBodyName				Text			NA
			Optional	No	(WFD database)				
17	Remarks	Remarks				Text	Remarks, comments or explanatory notes.	This field can be used to provide additional information about the record.	NA
			Optional	No	No				

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
1	Short name	Identifier (element)	Mandatory	Unique record [Primary Key]	Vocabulary	Data type	Definition	methodology	URL
2	Country code	CountryCode	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Text	Country code for the country of the sampling site.	See URL for vocabulary.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/datasets/latest/WI-SoE_Biology/tables/BiologyEQRCClassificationPro
3	Site ID	NationalSiteID	Mandatory	Yes	No	Text	Name of sampling site. Members can make up their own site ID (name).	The NationalSiteID can be made by data providers. The ID can contain letters, numbers and/or underscore (no spaces or special characters). NationalSiteID must be entered in both sheets in the reporting template: Site_AMR (one record for each NationalSiteID) and DisaggregatedData_AMR (NationalSiteID repeated for each sample).	NA
4	Sampling time	phenomenonTimeSamplingDate	Mandatory	Yes	No	Date	Date in which the sample was taken.	Use the format YYYY-MM-DD. If pooled DNA samples, choose the last sampling date.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/phenomenonTimeSamplingDate
5	Sample number	sampleIdentifier	Mandatory	Yes	No	Number	Unique sample identifier. Its main purpose is to distinguish multiple samples taken on the same day from the same location, and analyzed for the same determinand.	In case of replicate samples (multiple samples from the same site, date and determinand), enter a running number (1, 2, 3, ... etc.) to identify the replicates. If no replicates, enter the default value "1".	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/sampleIdentifier
6	Analysed matrix	procedureAnalysedMatrix	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Text	Matrix where the measurement has been made.	See table "Analysed matrix". Most relevant codes: W if direct cultivation from water sample. W-SPM if filtration and the matrix remaining on the filter is analyzed either for ARGs or ARBs.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/procedureAnalysedMatrix
7	Determinand code	observedPropertyDeterminandCode	Mandatory	Yes	Yes	Text	Unique code of the determinand monitored, as defined in the codelist.	See table "Determinand". It is also possible to enter additional genes not yet present in the vocabulary. Procedure: - Generate a gene/bacteria code based on the name; replace any space with underscore ("_"). - Enter the gene/bacteria code in the field "Determinand" in the reporting template (sheet "DisaggregatedData_AMR") - In the Remarks field, type "New determinand", and add any relevant information of the gene/bacteria, analysis or sampling.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/observedPropertyDeterminandCode

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
8	Unit of measure	resultUom	Mandatory	No	Yes	Text	Unit of measure for the reported values.	See table "Unit".	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/resultUom
9	Observed value	resultObservedValue	Mandatory	No	No	Number	Observed value (e.g. concentration) of the determinand in the sample.	Negative values are not allowed for AMR data. Zero values are allowed for ARBs data (Unit: CFU/dL), but not for ARGs data (Unit: Arg copy per 16S rRNA or gene copies/dL). If the measured concentration is below the limit of quantification (LOQ), then leave the "resultObservedValue" field empty, enter 'yes' the field "resultQualityObservedValueBelowLOQ", and fill in the field "procedureLOQValue".	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/resultObservedValue
10	Observed value below LOQ	resultQualityObservedValueBelowLOQ	Mandatory	No	Yes	Text	Flag to indicate whether the sample value was below the analytical limit of quantification (LOQ).	See table "Observed value below LOQ".	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/resultQualityObservedValueBelowLOQ
11	Limit of quantification	procedureLOQValue	Optional	No	No	Number	For qPCR absolute abundance: LOQ of the sample (lowest number of copies that could theoretically be quantified given the observed most diluted standard within the linear range of the standard curve (LOQ(sample)). For qPCR relative abundance to 16S: no LOQ, leave cell empty.	Write the Limit of Quantification for the sample analysis. Make sure the LOQ and the observed value use the same Unit of measure. It is required for determinands if "Observed Value Below LOQ" = 'yes', meaning the observed value was below the LOQ. For qPCR absolute abundance: calculation is "LOQ(sample) = LOQ(assay)*(sample dilution factor)*(extract elution volume [µl] / template volume [µl]) / (filtered sample volume [dL].	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/procedureLOQValue
12	Observation status flag	resultObservationStatus	Optional	No	Yes	Text	Status of the observed value in terms of its availability, relevancy, correctness or specifics of its source category.	See table "Observation status flag". Flags should only be used when value reported are outside of normal. If value is considered as "normal", leave the cell empty.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/resultObservationStatus
13	Remarks	Remarks	Optional	No	No	Text	Remarks, comments or explanatory notes.	This field can be used to provide additional information about the record. This element can be used to report recovery rates if preferred.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/Remarks

Short name	Analysed matrix		
Identifier	procedureAnalysedMatrix		
URL	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/Matrix/view		
Accepted codelist (copy paste from "Notation" into template)			
Notation	Label	Definition	URL
W	Water - Total	Whole sample (includes unknown values).	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/Matrix/W
W-DIS	Water - Dissolved (filtered)	Sample after filtering (filtrate)	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/Matrix/W-DIS
W-SPM	Water - Suspended particulate matter	Fraction remaining on the filter after filtering (residue)	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/Matrix/W-SPM
W-PDNA	Water - Pooled DNA samples	If pooling of DNA samples occurred.	NA

Short name	Water body category		
Identifier	parameterWaterBodyCategory		
URL	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/		
Accepted glossary (Copy paste from "Code" into the template)			
Code	Label	URL	
CW	Coastal water body	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/CW	
GW	Groundwater body	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/GW	
LW	Lake water body	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/LW	
MW	Marine waters	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/MW	
RW	River water body	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/RW	
TeW	Territorial waters	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/TeW	
TW	Transitional water body	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/WFDWaterBodyCategory/TW	
WW	Waste water to WWTP (Inlet to WWTP)	NA	
EW	Effluent from WWTP (outlet of WWTP)	NA	

Short name	Determinand		
Identifier	observedPropertyDeterminandCode		
URL	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/observedPropertyDeterminandCode		
Accepted code list (Copy paste from "Notation" to the template)			
Notation	Label	Use for unit...	Definition
16S_rRNA	16S rRNA	gene copies/dL	Marker for bacterial abundance.
Int1	Int1	gene copies/dL	An integron and marker for the process of horizontal gene transfer of plasmid-mediated resistance genes, such as tetracycline, sulfonamides, macrolides, beta-lactams, trimethoprim and quinolone.
blaCTX-Mx	blaCTX-Mx	gene copies/dL	Genes encoding CTX-Ms and a marker for ESBL.
ermB	ermB	gene copies/dL	Gene encoding a ribosomal methylase with ermC, that eventually reduces the affinity of macrolides and therefore macrolide resistance.
vanA	vanA	gene copies/dL	Gene cluster encoding vanomycin resistance and vanomycin like antibiotics resistance.
aadAx	aadAx	gene copies/dL	Marker gene for resistance to spectinomycin and streptomycin
tetW	tetW	gene copies/dL	Marker gene for bacterial tetracycline resistance
sul1	sul1	gene copies/dL	Gene encoding sul enzymes, and marker gene for sulfonamide resistance.
blaKPC	blaKPC	gene copies/dL	Gene encoding the enzyme Klebsiella pneumoniae carbapenemase (KPC), and causes carbapenem resistance.
ESBL	ESBL	[CFU]/dL	"Extended spectrum betalactamase", in this context meaning a ESBL producing bacteria giving rise to resistance against a broad spectrum of antibiotics through betalactamase production.
E._coli	E. coli	[CFU]/dL	Marker for <i>E.coli</i> abundance to standardize the proportion of ESBL-Ec.
Int1_16S	Int1	ARGcopy/16S	An integron and marker for the process of horizontal gene transfer of plasmid-mediated resistance genes, such as tetracycline, sulfonamides, macrolides, beta-lactams, trimethoprim and quinolone.
blaCTX-Mx_16S	blaCTX-Mx	ARGcopy/16S	Genes encoding CTX-Ms and a marker for ESBL.
ermB_16S	ermB	ARGcopy/16S	Gene encoding a ribosomal methylase with ermC, that eventually reduces the affinity of macrolides and therefore macrolide resistance.
vanA_16S	vanA	ARGcopy/16S	Gene cluster encoding vanomycin resistance and vanomycin like antibiotics resistance.
aadAx_16S	aadAx	ARGcopy/16S	Marker gene for resistance to spectinomycin and streptomycin
tetW_16S	tetW	ARGcopy/16S	Marker gene for bacterial tetracycline resistance
sul1_16S	sul1	ARGcopy/16S	Gene encoding sul enzymes, and marker gene for sulfonamide resistance.
blaKPC_16S	blaKPC	ARGcopy/16S	Gene encoding the enzyme Klebsiella pneumoniae carbapenemase (KPC), and causes carbapenem resistance.

Short name	Unit				
Identifier	resultUom				
URL	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/uom/				
Accepted code list (Copy paste from "Notation" into the template)					
Notation	Label	Status	Definition	URL	Comments
[CFU]/dL	Colony Forming Unit per deciliter	Valid	Colony Forming Unit per deciliter.	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/uom/[CFU].dL-1	Recommended for ARB
ARGcopy/16S	ARG copy per 16S rRNA		Relative abundance of gene copy number of antibiotic resistance gene per 16S rRNA gene copy number	NA	Recommended for ARG
genecopies/dL	Gene copies/dL		Absolute abundance of gene copy number of 16S rDNA itself. Should be calculated to the initial filtrated. See document for calculation scheme (https://eea1.sharepoint.com/:x:/r/teams/-EXT-Eionet/Shared%20Documents/WG%20Antimicrobial%20Resistance/Other%20activities/AMR%20pilot%20survey%202024/2024%20Environmental%20Results%20Calculation%20Template%20Eionet%20ESBL%20Ecoli.xlsx?d=wb2f7725b748a4fce8c93005637ce1696&csf=1&web=1&e=hloZrc)	NA	Recommended for ARG and 16S rDNA
ng/L	nanogram per litre	Valid	Mass concentration unit. Conversion factor: 1 kg/m ³ = 10 ⁹ ug/L	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/vocabulary/wise/uom/ng.L-1	
ARGcopy/mg{DNA}	ARG copy per mg DNA			NA	
ARGcopy/cell	ARGs copy per cell			NA	

Short name	Observed value below LOQ
Identifier	resultQualityObservedValueBelowLOQ
URL	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/resultQualityObservedValueBelowLOQ
Accepted codelist (Copy paste from "Code" into template)	
Code	Use if...
no	<p>... concentration was above or equal to the LOQ.</p> <p>... LOQ is not applicable to a specific determinand.</p> <p>... 'Observation Status' field contains the code indicating missing observed value and the field 'Observed Value' is empty.</p>
yes	... concentration value was below the LOQ.

Name	Observation status flag		
Identifier	resultObservationStatus		
URL	http://dd.eionet.europa.eu/dataelements/latest/resultObservationStatus		
Accepted glossary (Copy paste from "Code" into the template)			
Code	Label	Definition	URL
A	Record is confirmed as correct	Use this flag to speed up the data checking and processing. E.g. if the extremely high value of concentration is reported, it will be judged as an outlier by the automatic QA system and country will be asked to confirm or correct this value. With this flag described loop is removed. It is not necessary to apply this flag for all valid records. It is intended for confirmation of potential outliers or for other special cases where confirmation is needed or suitable.	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/fixdvalues/elem/95711/view/911309
L	Missing observed value, the data were not collected		https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/fixdvalues/elem/95711/view/911310
M	Missing observed value, the data can not exist	E.g. a given observed value source does not exist in the spatial unit, so the value can not be reported.	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/fixdvalues/elem/95711/view/911311
N	Missing observed value, observed value is not relevant or not significant		https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/fixdvalues/elem/95711/view/911312
O	Missing observed value, no further information is available	No further information is available as to the reason why the observed value is missing.	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/fixdvalues/elem/95711/view/911313
Z	Record reported in the past should be deleted	Use this flag to identify previously reported record that should be deleted (report the record again). Explanation can be provided in the Remarks field.	https://dd.eionet.europa.eu/fixdvalues/elem/95711/view/911317
R	Record reported as outside of efficiency rate of 90-110% for qPCR	If value had <90% or >110% efficiency rate for qPCR analysis. Explanations can be provided in the Remarks field	

A3.2 Data reporting template document

Instruction

For reporting of AMR data, please use two different files.

"WISE_AMR_template.xlsx" where you will fill in all the data and information from your sampling and analysis.

Enter the sample and analysis data in the sheet "DisaggregatedData_AMR".

Enter the sampling site information in the sheet "Site_AMR".

Please, name your filled-in template "WISE_AMR_<country code>_<YYYY-MM-DD>.xlsx". (example: WISE_AMR_NO_2024-03-08.xlsx).

"WISE_AMR_guidance.pdf" with instructions and where applicable, the vocabulary (code list).

Copy-paste from the vocabulary to the template is recommended to avoid spelling mistakes.

If you have information that does not fit in any of the elements in the template, please use the element/column "Remarks".

The guidance is provided with both a pdf-file and an excel-file, and the content is identical.

Definitions:

- Mandatory: 'Mandatory' = a number or text must be entered; 'Optional' = can be left empty.

- Unique record [Primary key]: The combination of elements that identify a unique record. To avoid duplicates, all records (rows) must have different combinations of the elements with Unique record [Primary key] = "yes".

- Vocabulary: : indicates a vocabulary (code list) exists for the given element. If "yes", the vocabulary for that element is given in a separate table in the guidance.

The filled-in template, stored as "WISE_AMR_<country code>_<YYYY-MM-DD>.xls", can be uploaded to the folder "Reporting" > folder for your landcode in Teams ([https://eea1.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/-EXT-](https://eea1.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/-EXT-Eionet/Shared%20Documents/WG%20Antimicrobial%20Resistance/Other%20activities/AMR%20data%20reporting/Reporting?csf=1&web=1&e=dgLA1L)

[Eionet/Shared%20Documents/WG%20Antimicrobial%20Resistance/Other%20activities/AMR%20data%20reporting/Reporting?csf=1&web=1&e=dgLA1L](https://eea1.sharepoint.com/:f:/r/teams/-EXT-Eionet/Shared%20Documents/WG%20Antimicrobial%20Resistance/Other%20activities/AMR%20data%20reporting/Reporting?csf=1&web=1&e=dgLA1L)).

Good luck with the AMR data reporting!

If you have any questions, please write in the teams channel of ETC-BE AMR.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q
1	Short name	Country code	Site ID	WWTP ID	Longitude	Latitude	Water body category code	WWTP name	National site name	Distance from sampling site to AMR source	Location of sampling site	WFD station name	WFD station name	River name	Water Body ID	Water Body Name	Remarks
2	Identifier (element)	CountryCode	NationalSiteID	WasteWaterTreatmentPlantID	Longitude	Latitude	parameterWaterBodyCategory	WasteWaterTreatmentPlantName	NationalSiteName	LengthFromSource	SiteLocation	WFDstation	WFD_EU_CD	RiverName	WaterBodyID	WaterBodyName	Remarks
3	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Optional	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional	Optional
4	Unique record [Primary key]	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
5	Vocabulary	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	(WFD database)	(WFD database)	(WFD database)	(WFD database)	(WFD database)	No
6	<i>Example 1</i>	NO	<i>IndreOslofjord123</i>	<i>(To be decided)</i>	<i>10.50041</i>	<i>59.79263</i>	<i>CW</i>	<i>VEAS (Vestfjorden Avlopsselskap)</i>	<i>Indre Oslofjord 123</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>Downstream</i>						
7	<i>Example 2</i>	NO	<i>IndreOslofjord456</i>	<i>(To be decided)</i>	<i>10.50043</i>	<i>59.79265</i>	<i>CW</i>	<i>VEAS (Vestfjorden Avlopsselskap)</i>	<i>Indre Oslofjord 456</i>	<i>50</i>	<i>Upstream</i>						

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M
1	Short name	Country code	Site ID	Sampling time	Sample number	Analysed matrix	Determinand code	Unit of measure	Observed value	Observed value below LOQ	Limit of quantification	Observation status flag	Remarks
2	Identifier (element)	CountryCode	NationalSiteID	phenomenonTimeSamplingDate	sampleIdentifier	procedureAnalysedMatrix	observedPropertyDeterminandCode	resultUom	resultObservedValue	resultQualityObservedValueBelowLOQ	procedureLOQValue	resultObservationStatus	Remarks
3	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory	Mandatory			
4	Unique record [Primary Key]	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes						
5	Vocabulary	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
6	Example 1	NO	IndreOslof jord123	2023-03-15	1	W-SPM	ermB	ARGcopy/16S	3,22E+08	no	0,5		Example 1 and 2 are replicates, but not reported as duplicates (they have different unique records).
7	Example 2	NO	IndreOslof jord123	2023-03-15	2	W-SPM	ermB	ARGcopy/16S		yes	0,5		
8	Example 3	NO	IndreOslof jord123	2023-03-15	1	W-SPM	16S_rRNA	genecopies/dL	3,22E+14	no	0,5	A	High value confirmed, therefore reported as "A".
9	Example 4	NO	IndreOslof jord123	2023-03-15	1	W-SPM	ESBL	[CFU]/dL	15	no			
10	Example 5	NO	IndreOslof jord456	2023-03-15	1	W-SPM	ESBL	[CFU]/dL	5	no			